

[Biomarker Analytical Laboratories](#)

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Title: SOP for metabolite profiling of seminal plasma via GC Orbitrap

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Summary

Seminal plasma chemical profiles provide distinct and metabolic phenotypes suited for fertility study monitoring. Profiling via GC-MS is favourable as it provides robust measures across many core primary metabolic pathways; including amino acids, TCA metabolites, carbohydrates and some lipids (e.g. steroids & fatty acid). A protocol for simple preparation of seminal plasma samples intended to undergo GC-MS analysis is described and enables large-scale semi-quantitative profiling.

Preparation

Safety information

- Seminal plasma is classified as a biohazardous material & thus all items in contact (e.g. pipette tips, vials) should be disposed of appropriately.
- All work should be conducted in fume hood.
 - MeOx: Danger - corrosive, harmful, health hazard, environmental hazard
 - Pyridine: Danger - harmful, flammable
 - MSTFA: Warning - harmful, flammable
 - C₇-C₄₀ alkane series (heptane) – flammable, harmful, health hazard, environmental hazard

Equipment

- 10 µL, 100 µL & 1 mL pipettes
- Centrifugal evaporator
- Storage boxes for 2 mL vials
- Heat block for glass vials
- Mini vortex
- Centrifuge with rotor for 1.5 mL Eppendorf vials
- Box with ice

Consumables & glassware

- 2 mL screw cap glass autosampler vials with built-in 200 µL insert and caps (PTFE septa)

- 4 mL screw cap glass vial and cap
- 1.5 mL Eppendorf vial
- 10 μ L, 100 μ L & 1 mL tips
- Labels for 1.5 and 2 mL vials

Reagents

- Seminal plasma stored in -80 °C freezer and thawed at room temperature
- Methanol, LC-MS grade
- Chloroform, LC-MS grade
- GC grade anhydrous pyridine >99% purity
 - Pyridine will discolour to yellow if old or impure.
- C₇-C₄₀ alkane series mix (10 μ g/mL in pyrimidin/or isooctane)
- PCBs mix (1 μ g/mL in pyridine/or isooctane)
- Methoxyamine hydrochloride (MeOx) > 97.5%
 - MeOx reacts with carbonyl groups (e.g. ketones, aldehydes) to form oxime and prevent numerous enol forms that gives rise to many peaks, especially for reducing sugars.
- N-methyl-N-(trimethylsilyl)trifluoroacetamide (MSTFA) > 98%
 - MSTFA replaces free hydroxyl groups with trimethylsilyl (TMS) to reduce polarity and increase volatility (alcohol > phenol > carboxylic acid > amine > amide).
 - Alternatively can use MSTFA + 1% trimethylchlorosilane (TMCS) as an extra catalyst if many sites observed to be unreacted. (Typically, does not make a difference when using pyridine).

MeOx solution (20 mg/mL in pyridine)

- For 3 mL of solution, weigh 60 mg methoxyamine hydrochloride into glass tube.
- Add 3 mL of pyridine and vortex until dissolved.
 - Solution can be kept for 3 days at room temp. Store double wrapped (e.g. parafilm cap and place glass tube in plastic falcon).

Standards

[²H₄] Succinic acid (99% isotope enrichment) – corrosive, harmful

[²H₂₇] Myristic acid (98% isotope enrichment) - harmful

Procedure

Standard preparation

1. Prepare 1 mL aliquot of stock [²H₄] Succinic acid c = 100 μ g/mL in methanol
2. Prepare 1 mL aliquot of stock [²H₂₇] Myristic acid c = 100 μ g/mL in chloroform

3. Pipette directly or dry the internal reference standard mix down in Centrifugal evaporator at laboratory temperature, store in $-80\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and reconstitute in the solvent before analysis.

Sample preparation

1. NOTE: Store seminal plasma samples at $-80\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ in a glass tubes
2. Refrigerate sample at laboratory temperature
3. Vortexed for 10 seconds, centrifuge for 10 minutes at 4000 RPM
4. Pipette $10\text{ }\mu\text{L}$ of the supernatant to 1.5 mL glass vials with built-in $200\text{ }\mu\text{L}$ insert
5. Pipette $10\text{ }\mu\text{L}$ of $[^2\text{H}_4]$ Succinic acid $c = 100\text{ }\mu\text{g/mL}$ in methanol
6. Pipette $10\text{ }\mu\text{L}$ of $[^2\text{H}_{27}]$ Myristic acid $c = 100\text{ }\mu\text{g/mL}$ in chloroform
7. For every 10 samples prepare 1 QC sample (pool of seminal plasma), 1 processing blank (pipetting $10\text{ }\mu\text{L}$ of milliQ water). QC sample and processing blank are prepared with samples
8. Dry the sample down in Centrifugal evaporator at laboratory temperature, store in $-80\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$
9. Derivatize dried samples

Sample derivatisation

1. Remove samples from freezer, decap and leave for 20 minutes in fume hood.
 - a. Moisture prevents derivatisation reaction.
2. Pre-heat dry heat block to $60\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$.
3. Add $30\text{ }\mu\text{L}$ MeOX solution to each dried sample
4. Cap immediately and incubate in a heating block for 60 minutes at $60\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$
5. Add $70\text{ }\mu\text{L}$ of MSTFA to each sample
6. Cap immediately and incubate in a heating block for 60 minutes at $60\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$
7. After the time has elapsed cooled down samples for 2 minutes on ice
 - o Cap and measure on GC-Q Exactive immediately or maximum within 24 hours/ If required, replace vials caps prior to re-injection of sample.

GC-MS analysis

2. Before measurement replace liner and septa per ~150-200 samples
3. Calibrate and Tune MS
4. Input sequence
5. Start GC-MS analysis run
6. Check initial blanks, alkane series, PCBs series and QC samples.
 - If problems, stop run, wrap samples in parafilm and store at -20 °C whilst troubleshooting.
 - Can do initial checks of blanks / alkane series/PCBs series prior to derivatisation if samples are precious.

GC sequence setup

1. Pyridine blank
2. Alkanes
3. PCBs
4. Pyridine blank
5. Pyridine blank
6. QC_dilution series in 3 replicates (same sample preparation as QC with 2x, 4x, 8x, 16x, 32x, 64x dilution & spiked with labeled standards same as QC (samples))
7. Procedural blank
8. QC sample
9. Samples 1-10
10. Procedural blank
11. QC sample
12. Sample 11-20
13. Procedural blank
14. End with Alkanes, PCBs and 3 pyridine blanks

GC-MS method setup

Autosampler settings

TriPlus RSH Autosampler		Comments
General		
Injection port		
Injector	Injector A (SSL)	
Type	Single	
Injection mode		
Mode	Basic	
Rapid mode		
Rapid mode	Disable	
Syringe type		
Syringe volume (µL)	10	
Needle length (mm)	57	
Sampling		
Sample volume (µL)	2	*Set in method sequence to be 1 µL*
Plunger strokes	0	
Air and filling mode	Custom	
Air volume (µL)	0	
Filling volume (µL)	0	
Sampling depth in vials		
Sample vial depth (mm)	\	
Bottom sense	Yes	
Height from bottom (mm)	1.5	
Injection		
Injection depth	Custom	
Pre-injection dwell time (s)	0	
Post-injection dwell time (s)	0.1	
Fast injection	Off	
Injection depth (mm)	45	
Penetration speed (mm/s)	90	
Injection Speed (µL/s)	50.0	
Sample viscosity		
Sample type	Custom	
Sample pullup speed (µL/s)	0.4	
Delay after plunger strokes (s)	1.5	
Viscosity delay (s)	2	
Washes		
Washes		Solvent A: nonane
		Solvent B: toluene
Number of solvents(s)	Multiple	Solvent C: acetone
Wash station	Standard wash station	Solvent D: nonane
Pre-injection		E position: waste

Solvent	A	\	\	\
Cycles			4	
Solvent volume (uL)			7.0	
Rinse				
Rinses			0	
Rinse Volume (uL)			1	
Post-injection				
Solvent	\	B	C	D
Cycles			7	
Solvent volume (uL)			7.0	
Sync				
GC synchro start				
Synchro type			Standard	
Advanced				
Advanced parameters				
Wash solvent depth (mm)			45	
Waste depth (mm)			10	
Needle speed in vial (mm/s)			10	
Solvent filling speed (uL/s)			1	
Bubble elimin. pullup (uL/s)			5	
Delay between strokes (s)			2.0	

GC settings

TRACE 1310 Series GC

Oven

Ramps

	Rate (°C/min)	Temp (°C)	Hold time (min)
Initial		80	0.5
1	40	200	0.5
2	40	260	0.5
3	55	330	4.0

Options

Max temp.	340 °C
Prep-run timeout	10 min
Equilibration time	1 min
Ready delay	0.00 min
Oven on	Yes

Comments

Trace 1310
Column: Rxi-5SiIMS (15m x 0.25 mm x 0.25 um) with 2m guard (0.25 mm) at transfer & 2m guard (0.53 mm) at inlet.

S/SL (front)

S/SL mode Split

Inlet

Temp On 290 °C

Split flow On 24.0 mL/min

Split ratio 20

Splitless time 0.80 min

Surge

Surge pressure 140.00 kPA

Surge duration 0.80 min

Septum purge

Purge flow 3.0 mL/min

Constant septum purge Yes

Stop purge for \

Carrier mode Constant flow

Carrier flow

Flow On 1.2 mL/min

Carrier options

Vacuum compensation On

Carrier gas saver On

Gas saver flow 15.0 mL/min

Gas saver time 3.00 min

Aux. Temperatures

Auxilliary temperature control

Transfer Line 1 On 280 °C

Transfer Line 2 On 280 °C

Septa: Merlin microseal
Liner: Restek Topaz 4.0mm precision
liner w/ wool

MS settings

Q Exactive GC-Orbitrap MS

Global Settings

User role Advanced

Use lock masses off

Lock mass injection \

Time

Method duration 11.5 min

Customized Tolerances (+/-)

Lock Masses \

Inclusion \

Exclusion — \

Comments

Mass Tags	—	\
Dynamic Exclusion		\
EI/CI Source		
Filament on delay		2.00 min
MS transfer line temp		250 °C
Ion source temp		280 °C
Ionization mode		EI
CI gas type		None
CI gas flow		0.00 mL/min
Use tune emission current		FALSE
Emission current		50.0 µA
Use tune electron energy		FALSE
Electron energy		70 eV
Use tune file C-Trap energy offset		TRUE
C-Trap energy offset		0.0 V
Cal gas level		Off
 Properties of Full MS-SIM		
Experiment		Full MS — SIM
General		
Runtime		2 to 11.5 min
Polarity		Positive
Full MS		
Microscans		1
Resolution		60,000
AGC target		1.00E+06
Maximum IT		auto
Scan range		70 to 700 m/z
Spectrum data type		Profile
 Setup		
Tunefiles		
General		
Switch Count	0	
Base Tunefile	C:\Xcalibur\methods\EI_20200605_EP-IT50_250_280.mstune	
Tune scan range		70-700
Res		60,000
AGC		1.00E+06
Max inject		auto
MS transfer		250
Ion source		280

Update each acquisition - Tune to TIC